

Acute toxicity assessment of diarrhetic shellfish toxins by voluntary feeding in mice

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ABSTRACT

Diarrhetic shellfish toxins (DSTs) and phytoplankton species producing them have been frequently reported in seawater worldwide. They accumulate in shellfish and pose a significant threat to the environment and the health of seafood consumers. The goal of this study was to evaluate the acute toxicity of DSTs administered to mice via voluntary ingestion through bread. This is a method for the delivery of DSTs that provided convenient dosing, reduced animal stress and mimicked human exposure more accurately than oral gavage administration. Over 24 h, key parameters including clinical signs were meticulously recorded. The results showed a dose-dependent reduction in food and water consumption and significant relative body weight loss, with OA and DTX1 inducing more pronounced gastrointestinal disturbances at lower doses than DTX2. This is the first study to compare toxicity of DSTs administered by voluntary feeding where diarrhea is the main symptom. Effective dose 50 for watery diarrhea in the first 3 h highlighted that DTX2 is significantly less toxic than OA and DTX1. These insights enhance our comprehension of DSTs toxicity and contribute to the risk assessment of the dietary exposure of DSTs from shellfish.

1. Introduction

Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins (DSTs) are synthesized by dinoflagellates of the genera *Prorocentrum* and *Dinophysis* and include okadaic acid (OA) and dinophysistoxins (James et al., 2010). These compounds represent a significant threat to human health due to their accumulation in filter-feeding organisms such as bivalve molluscs (Vilarinho et al., 2018; Yasumoto et al., 1978). After ingestion they cause Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP), which manifests in gastrointestinal symptoms like diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, and abdominal cramps following accidental ingestion. While fatalities are rare, the intoxication can severely affect public health and lead to significant economic losses in the seafood industry (Chen et al., 2018; Reguera et al., 2012)

The oral toxicity of DSTs is complex, and the mechanism of toxicity is not clear. OA is known to inhibit protein phosphatases, particularly PP1 and PP2A, which are involved in numerous cellular pathways and contribute to some effects of the toxin (Louzao et al., 2005; Takai et al.,

1992). However, this mechanism of action is not responsible for the toxic effects of DSTs (Espiña et al., 2010; Munday, 2013). There are also differences in DSTs potency. The relative toxicity of dinophysistoxins compared to OA after administration to mice by oral gavage or intraperitoneal have been a subject of evaluation (Abal et al., 2017; Aune et al., 2012; Park et al., 2023). Intraperitoneal administration studies have shown that OA has similar toxicity to dinophysistoxin 1 (DTX1), while dinophysistoxin 2 (DTX2) is less potent (Aune et al., 2007). However, comparison of lethal doses by oral administration have reached different conclusion: DTX1 is more potent than OA (Abal et al., 2017, 2018).

While previous studies have demonstrated some acute toxic effects of OA in various animal models, including mice, the full complexity of its toxicology and the impact on intestinal health, remains incompletely elucidated (Liu et al., 2020; Munday, 2013; Park et al., 2023). Some investigations have shown that OA accumulates in the liver and may undergo enterohepatic circulation (Louzao et al., 2021a; Matias et al.,

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1999). Histological studies have indicated that OA induce some epithelial erosion, villous shortening and edema, especially in the small intestine, though these effects do not always correlate with the onset of diarrhea (Aune et al., 2012; Ito et al., 2002). These structural changes suggest that OA could disrupt the normal ion transport processes responsible for water and electrolyte absorption (Costas et al., 2022; Engevik and Engevik, 2021). Serotonin, produced by enterochromaffin cells and serotonergic neurons in the gut, regulates both fluid secretion and motility and it has been implicated in the pathophysiology of diarrhea induced by different toxins (Mawe and Hoffman, 2013; Rao, 2019). Recently, it has been reported the involvement of serotonin (5-HT) in OA-induced diarrhea (Louzao et al., 2021b). However, the mechanisms underlying OA toxicity remains a subject of ongoing research.

The route of human exposure to DSTs is the ingestion of seafood contaminated by toxins, although different organisms may become exposed to these compounds through other routes. New findings indicate that OA may be converted into other metabolites in the gut, further complicating the assessment of its toxicity (Liu et al., 2022). To mitigate health risks, agencies around the world perform regular monitoring and establish the legal limit of 160 µg equivalents OA/kg of shellfish meat for marine products destined at human consumption (Commission, 2004). Risk assessments of these toxins require toxicity equivalency factors (TEFs) which represent the relative toxicities of analogues compared to OA as reference compound. Even though no human death by DSTs has been reported, its current TEF values are based on acute lethality. Acute toxicity studies after oral gavage administration of toxin, reported variability in the lethal dose 50 (LD50) between 400 and 900 µg/kg (Aune et al., 2012; Ito et al., 2002; Le Hégarat et al., 2006), or even above 1000 µg/kg (Tubaro et al., 2003). Discrepancies in toxicity values may largely stem from the use of non-certified standards, affecting the accuracy of toxicological assessments (Botana et al., 2017). Also, oral administration by gavage can overestimate the toxicity of shellfish toxins (Boundy et al., 2021). Therefore, voluntary feeding has emerged as a preferable method for toxicological studies being representative of human consumption and more reliable than oral gavage (Botana, 2012). This approach as well as the use of certified standards of toxins provide convenient dosing, minimizes animal stress, avoids complications associated with gavage, and ensures a more physiologically relevant assessment of oral toxicity.

This research aims to integrate *in vivo* acute toxicity data of OA, DTX1, and DTX2 when administered by voluntary intake. The described approach properly reflects the symptoms of DSTs, such as diarrhea without death with adequate predictions for acute toxin exposure from shellfish consumption. We evaluated key parameters such as food and water consumption, body weight, presence and severity of diarrhea, and toxin excretion to determine the different toxicological profiles of these marine toxins and better evaluate the health risk.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

OA, DTX1 and DTX2 were provided by Laboratorio CIFGA S.A. (Lugo, Spain) with purity > 98 % as Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). Stock solutions of the toxins were prepared in ethanol and stored at -80°C.

2.2. Animals

Female Swiss (ICR background) mice, 4 weeks old, were purchased from the Centre for Experimental Biomedicine (CEBEGA) of the University of Santiago de Compostela. Animals were acclimatized to standard conditions for 1 week prior to the experiments. They were maintained under standard conditions: light/dark cycles (12 h/12 h) in a room controlled in temperature (22 ± 2 °C) and humidity (60–70 %),

with free access to water and pelleted food. Then, mice were weighed (mean weight 21 g, with individual weight variation not exceeding ± 20 %).

2.3. Procedure for *in vivo* experiment

Mice were randomly distributed into four groups (n = 3/dose): OA-treated (1, 10, 100, 250, 400, 500, 750, 1000 µg/kg bw), DTX1-treated (10, 50, 100, 250, 500, 750 µg/kg bw), DTX2-treated (10, 100, 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1500, 2000, 3000 µg/kg bw) and control. To ensure familiarity with bread as a toxin delivery method, the animals were introduced to it 5 days before the study began as previously described (Rodríguez-Santos et al., 2024). Prior dosing the mice were weighed and housed individually in metabolic cages.

Freshly prepared toxin solutions were diluted in 0.9 % saline. A 100 mg piece of bread was infused with 30 µL of the toxin solution and placed in the cages for voluntary intake. Control animals received bread containing only the vehicle solution. Mice voluntarily ingested the toxic bread in less than 10 min.

After dosing, mice had unrestricted access to food and water for all the experiment. Body weight was recorded at the beginning and 24 h post-treatment. Food and water intake were registered, and clinical signs were systematically monitored throughout the study. Symptoms were recorded throughout the experiment. During the experimental period feces were observed and some of them collected. The severity of diarrhea, the main symptom of DSTs, was assessed using a scoring system. Stool consistency was defined as follows: 0 (normal stools), 1 (slightly loose stools), 2 (unformed loose stools), 3 (watery diarrhea), and 4 (persistent watery diarrhea with repeated episodes in less than 20 min).

All animal procedures were performed in accordance with European (EU directive 2010/63/EU) and Spanish legislation (Real Decreto 53/2013, Decreto 296/2008), and all procedures were accepted by the Institutional Animal Care Committee of the University of Santiago de Compostela (01/17/LU-002).

At the end of the experimental period (24 h), mice were euthanized by CO₂ inhalation, and subsequent necropsies were conducted. The main organs (heart, lungs, liver, stomach, large and small intestine, kidney, and brain) were collected and weighed in each group of mice.

2.4. Blood analysis

Blood samples collected in heparin coated tubes were analysed for biochemical parameters. Only samples from animals that survived the 24 h experiment were collected. Following centrifugation, 100 µL were loaded into Health Checking Profile and measured in Chemistry Analyzer Pointcare® cV3 MNCHIP. Health Checking Profile included blood glucose, albumin, globulin, total bilirubin, creatinine, cholesterol, Alanine Transaminase (ALT), phosphorus and amylase.

Blood samples were also analysed for hematological parameters using the ProCyte Dx® hematology analyzer (Idexx Laboratories). The analysis comprised total erythrocyte count, total leukocyte count, lymphocytes count, percentages of neutrophils, monocytes and eosinophils.

2.5. Toxin analysis

During the experimental period (2, 6, 12 and 24) feces of mice that received 100 µg/kg DSTs by voluntary feeding were observed, collected and weighed. DSTs were extracted with methanol as previously described (Louzao et al., 2021a). Briefly, 0.1 g of homogenized feces were extracted with 400 µL methanol. After mixing vortex for 1 min and sonication for 30 s, the mixtures were centrifuged at 4000 rpm (2486 × g) for 10 min. Supernatants were transferred to microtubes, and the pellets underwent two additional extractions. The combined supernatants were then evaporated to dryness and reconstituted in 100 µL of methanol. Next, 40 µL of methanol and 10 µL of 10 % trichloroacetic

acid were added to enhance protein precipitation. Then, 50 μL acetonitrile was added, and the final extracts were filtered through a 0.2 μm membrane and centrifugated at 1400 $\times g$ for 10 min before analysis by UPLC-MS/MS.

2.6. Statistical analysis

In vivo results were analysed using the Kruskal-Wallis test followed Dunnett's Multiple Comparison test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Statistical and graphical analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism 5.0.

3. Results

3.1. Biological parameters and clinical signs

Mice voluntarily ingested the toxic bread in less than 10 min. The effect of different doses of OA, DTX1, and DTX2 on biological parameters were registered 24 h after toxin administration. Treated mice showed a significant dose-dependent decrease in food intake compared to controls (Fig. 1A). Mice that received DTX1 showed a very robust reduction in food consumption at doses higher than 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, while mice with DTX2 only doses higher than 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ dramatically decrease food intake. Water consumption was significantly reduced in mice treated with all the toxins versus controls (Fig. 1B). This decrease was more evident in mice administered with OA at doses higher than 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, while in mice with DTX2 this effect was evident at 1500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Body weights were recorded pre-administration and then 24 h later to note any changes (Fig. 1C). Control mice showed an increase in body weight. Significant reductions in body weight (%) were observed with OA at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and higher and with DTX1 higher than 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, while no significant effects were detected for DTX2.

During necropsy, to compare signs of toxicity, a categorization system was established based on the damage observed in the stomach, small intestine, and large intestine, using a scale from 0 to 2, where 0 indicated normal appearance and 2 severe damage or large fluid accumulation. Controls always have 0 scores. The gastrointestinal index

(GI) was then calculated by adding the score of each of the three organs for each mouse (ranging from 0 to 6) and the mean presented in Fig. 1D.

GI scores exceeded the intermediate damage threshold (GI = 3) at 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX1, and 750 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX2, indicating important gastrointestinal alterations at these doses.

Symptoms recorded throughout the experiment were orbital tightening, apathy, lordosis, piloerection, ear position, cyanosis, tremors, nose bulge, dyspnea and hunched position.

Notably, the number of symptoms rapidly increased in both OA- and DTX1-treated mice in a dose-dependent way, whereas DTX2-treated mice exhibited lower number of symptoms and with less severity (Fig. 2). Individual variability was particularly evident in the DTX2 group, where symptoms such as orbital tightening, piloerection or tremors were less commonly observed compared to the other treatments.

Diarrhea is the main symptom of toxicity in mice that received DSTs by voluntary ingestion. The score in feces was carefully documented (Fig. 3). It indicates the severity of diarrhea and was dose-dependent. DTX1-treated mice displayed clear signs of gastrointestinal disease and high diarrhea scores in the first 3 h even at low doses. Mice that received OA exhibited severe diarrhea, at 1 and 3 h, coinciding with other toxicity signs. In contrast, DTX2-treated mice showed lower diarrhea scores at almost all time points and doses. Only mice with doses higher than 1500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX2 had feces with score 3 in the first hours after administration. As expected, no diarrhea was observed in control animals at any time point.

The Fig. 4 shows the percentage of mice that presented watery diarrhea (Score ≥ 3) in the first 3 h after treatment with DSTs. Based on the nonlinear regression curve fit the dose of OA, DTX1, and DTX2 that induced watery diarrhea in 50 % of mice was estimated (ED₅₀). These doses were 275 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for DTX1, 302 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for OA and 1202 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for DTX2, which indicated that DTX2 is less toxin than the other two. With these doses based on the main DSTs toxicity symptom, we can set TEF values (OA 1; DTX1 1.1; DTX2 0.25) that ensure accurate risk assessment.

In addition, the organ/body weight ratio of the liver, stomach, small intestine and large intestine, was recorded (Fig. 5). A moderate, non-

Fig. 1. Dose-response effect of OA, DTX1, and DTX2 at 24 h as Mean \pm SEM. A: Food consumption (g), B: Water consumption (mL), C: Δ Body weight (%), and D: Gastrointestinal index (GI). Kruskal-Wallis Test with Dunnett's Multiple Comparison was performed. Statistical significance compared to the control is indicated as * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), and *** ($p < 0.001$). Doses are expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

Fig. 2. Unspecific symptoms observed in mice administered with OA, DTX1, and DTX2 over time. Overall number of symptoms recorded, including orbital tightening, apathy, lordosis, piloerection, ear position, cyanosis, tremors, nose bulge, dyspnea and hunched position. Mean \pm SEM.

significant decrease in liver/body weight ratio was observed in the high dose groups of toxins (Fig. 5A). From 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA and DTX1 onwards, changes in liver color were observed, with pale or dark parts, as well as a granulated texture. Stomach/body weight ratio (Fig. 5B) showed an increase in toxin treated mice, only significant at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX1 with no significant changes in the stomach injury indicators. In the small intestine/body weight ratio (Fig. 5C), a non-significant increase was observed at low-media doses, followed by a decrease at high doses, being significant at 500 and 750 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA. In the large intestine/body weight ratio (Fig. 5D) significant reductions were registered starting at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX1.

Table S1 illustrates the mortality in mice that received the DSTs by voluntary ingestion. This was registered between 6 and 24 h after administration. The mortality within 24 h was 100 % in the dose 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ of the OA group. DTX1 caused mortality to mice exposed to dose 750 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. However, mortality was only registered in mice that received DTX2 by voluntary feeding at doses of 1500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and above.

3.2. Hematology and blood biochemical analysis

Results of the hematological analysis of blood collected from mice 24 h post-administration of DSTs by voluntary intake are presented in Fig. S1. There were no significant effects of any of the toxins on erythrocytes. A decreasing trend was observed for lymphocytes in mice that received OA at doses higher than 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, even though monocytes displayed an increasing trend, and neutrophils showed a significant increase in percentage. Neutrophils also showed increases in mice with DTX1 that was significant at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Monocytes increased at higher doses of OA and DTX1 with statistical significance in the dose 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA.

Figs. S2 and S3 show the biochemical analysis of blood collected from mice 24 h after administration of DSTs by voluntary feeding. Glucose shows a slight decrease, with significant reductions at 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ OA and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX1. Whereas albumin decreases with all three toxins being significant with OA at doses higher than 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and with DTX2 at doses 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and higher. Only significant differences in blood globulin were detected in mice with 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ DTX2. OA and DTX1 elicited non-significant decrease in blood levels of bilirubin at

Fig. 3. Diarrhea score observed in mice administered with OA, DTX1, and DTX2 over time, represented as mean ± SEM.

24 h.

3.3. Toxin fecal excretion

The excretion profiles of OA, DTX1 and DTX2 were analysed in fecal samples of mice treated with 100 µg/kg over 24 h using linear regression fit. Fig. 6 presents the percentage of each toxin excretion relative to the total dose administered.

The fecal excretion dynamics of the three toxins followed a similar pattern. Even though 50 % of the dose of OA and DTX2 was already eliminated at 20.7 and 20.5 h respectively, but after 24 h only 47 % DTX1 was excreted.

4. Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of the acute effects

of increasing doses of DSTs, (OA, DTX1 and DTX2), administered by voluntary feeding which better reflects the actual situation of human intake of toxins in seafood. We observed a dose-dependent highly reduction in food and water intake in mice with OA and DTX1 affecting these parameters at lower doses compared to DTX2. Feeding mice just once with bread contaminated with DSTs resulted in a significant decrease of food consumption within 24 h, at doses higher than 50 µg/kg for DTX1 and 100 µg/kg for OA, but the dose must increase to 1000 µg/kg to detect a significant reduction with DTX2. This was consistent with previous experimental findings when DSTs were administered to mice by oral gavage (Abal et al., 2018; Louzao et al., 2021b; Sosa et al., 2022). Alongside the reduction in food and therefore energy intake, there was also a decrease in water ingestion. Mice showed a significant decrease in water consumption at very low doses for all the toxins evaluated. Even though this reduction was more evident in mice administered with DTX1 at doses higher than 100 µg/kg and higher than

Fig. 4. Percentage of mice treated with DSTs that presented watery diarrhea in the first 3 h. Dose of OA, DTX1 and DTX2 that induced diarrhea with Score ≥ 3 in 50 % of mice were specified. R^2 values: OA = 0.9393, DTX1 = 0.9056, and DTX2 = 0.7400.

Fig. 5. Organ/body weight ratio of liver (A), stomach (B), small intestine (C) and large intestine (D) in control mice and mice treated with the different doses of OA, DTX1 and DTX2. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Kruskal-Wallis Test with Dunnett's Multiple Comparison was performed. Significant differences from the control group are indicated as * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$) and *** ($p < 0.001$).

400 µg/kg with OA, while in mice with DTX2 this effect was evident at 1500 µg/kg. These effects could be indicative of discomfort and pain.

These effects on ingestion of food and water were accompanied by changes in body weight. A significant decrease in relative body weight at 24 h was observed in mice that received OA or DTX1 by voluntary feeding while no significant weight loss was observed in mice administered with DTX2. This effect of DTX1 was dose-dependent starting at 100 µg/kg but with OA starts at 250 µg/kg. Like our findings, that loss of body weight by OA and DTX1 was previously reported when toxins were administered by oral gavage (Aune et al., 2012; Sosa et al., 2022). This weight loss was also found after repeated doses of OA and DTX1 being a common physiological parameter that reflects the overall health status (Park et al., 2023).

Furthermore, we examined the effects of DSTs on the fluid

accumulation in stomach and intestine. We evaluated it with the GI value that showed a dose-dependent increase with all DSTs indicating perturbation of normal digestive function. Fluid retention in mice has been previously reported with OA (Aune et al., 2012; Costas et al., 2022; Sosa et al., 2022; Tubaro et al., 2003). In our study DTX1 seems more potent in inducing damage to the digestive organs, with intermediate alterations observed in the stomach and intestine at a dose as low as 100 µg/kg. Local damage to the GI tract leads to decreased appetite and consequent weight loss. Organ injury was also assessed by the relative organ weight. Liver weight showed a moderate non-significant decrease in mice with toxins. Interestingly, a dose-dependent non-significant increase in ALT has also been observed for OA and DTX1, indicating liver injury as previously reported by oral and intraperitoneal administration (Park et al., 2023; Tubaro et al., 2004, 2003), although no changes were

Fig. 6. Percentage of cumulative excretion of OA (A), DTX1 (B) and DTX2 (C) excreted in feces versus time (h). The grey circles represent the mean values, and individual replicates are shown as empty black circles.

observed at lower OA doses (Sosa et al., 2022). Small serum creatinine increases are insufficient to indicate any renal dysfunction. Stomach weight increased in mice that received DTX1 which could be consistent with cell swelling and congestion. In addition, macroscopic changes were observed in the organ showing contents with a liquid-gas consistency. This condition was recorded in the GI. Previous studies described that mouse exposed to OA by oral gavage had moderately dilated stomachs with watery contents (Aune et al., 2012). This swelling could be due to retention of gastric contents as well as mucosal damage, highlighting the gastrointestinal effects of these toxins. By the voluntary administration of OA mouse showed significant decrease in the small intestine at dose higher than 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, possibly reflecting reduced food and water intake. 24 h after OA and DTX1 voluntary ingestion the weight of large intestine also showed a significant decrease at the highest doses of toxins. Necropsies in both cases revealed diarrhetic contents.

The hematological parameters and blood biochemical profile help us evaluate systemic effects of DSTs. They caused leukopenia but not anemia as was previously reported (Wu et al., 2016). This decrease in leukocytes was greater with OA. Leukopenia apparently resulted from a reduction in the number of lymphocytes and eosinophils as previously described by (Sosa et al., 2022), which may be due to direct toxicity leading to necrosis, and subsequently agranulocytosis (European Commission: Joint Research et al., 2023). Neutrophils and monocytes accumulation with OA and DTX1 may indicate an inflammatory response. These effects were more pronounced and appeared at lower doses of OA and DTX1, suggesting an increased sensitivity to these toxins.

Clinically, treated mice exhibited up to 10 symptoms as early indicators of DST-induced toxicity. Our results indicate that both OA and DTX1 induced a rapid onset of these symptoms which increased with the dose administered especially in DTX1 treated mice. In contrast, mice that received DTX2 consistently showed a milder toxicity profile, with fewer symptoms at similar doses. These results agree with previous reports in rats exposed to DSTs, where an early inappetence and inactivity was observed (Liu et al., 2020), also anorexia and dyspnea was documented in DSTs treated mice (Aune et al., 2012). In addition, the occurrence of several symptoms, such as piloerection, lordosis and

cyanosis, following exposure to OA were previous reported (Louzao et al., 2021a; Tubaro et al., 2003). The mean number of symptoms observed along the time was lower for DTX2 also occurred at higher doses than for DTX1 or OA (Abal et al., 2017, 2018). Overall, the rapid manifestation of non-specific symptoms in OA and DTX1 treatments contrasts with the milder appearance in DTX2-treated animals when received the toxins by voluntary ingestion. Our findings consistently indicate that DTX2 toxicity is significantly lower than OA and DTX1. Even though the cumulative fecal excretion dynamics of the three toxins followed a similar pattern, the percentage of DTX1 excreted at 24 h was only 47 % while 50 % of OA and DTX2 were already eliminated via feces by 20 h. Therefore, DTX1 remains in the body for longer, which can lead to greater toxicity.

As expected, diarrhea was the main symptom of DSP in our study, with distinct temporal and dose-dependent profiles among the three DSTs. In the first 3 h after voluntary intake, OA and DTX1-treated mice exhibited watery diarrhea (Score ≥ 3) with low-medium doses, indicating severe early acute toxicity. In contrast, DTX2-treated mice maintained lower scores with a modest increase to score of 2 or 3 at high doses (Abal et al., 2017). Furthermore, at doses of 1500 and 2000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, DTX2 induced repeated episodes of watery diarrhea suggesting potential differences in intestinal motility between these toxins (Abal et al., 2017). After 24 h, both the OA and DTX1 groups maintained persistent feces with mean scores between 1 and 2 whereas most DTX2-treated animals had normal stools (score 0). This is in line with previous reports documenting rapid gastrointestinal disturbances following DST exposure by oral gavage (Abal et al., 2017; Ito et al., 2002; Louzao et al., 2021a; Tubaro et al., 2003), even at low doses of OA and DTX1 (Matias et al., 1999; Park et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Santos et al., 2024). Direct action of DSTs in the intestine and/or at the neurointestinal level could be the trigger for hypersecretion and acute diarrhea (Ito et al., 2002; Louzao et al., 2021b; Reale et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2012). Our results highlighted that DSTs induced a rapid onset of feces within the first 3 h after voluntary ingestion but severity and progression of diarrhea varies between analogues. We determined the dose for the incidence of acute diarrhea in 50 % of mice (ED_{50}). In mice that received OA and DTX1 by voluntary intake the values were 302 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 275 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ respectively, suggesting similar acute toxicity (Park et al., 2023). In contrast, this dose

for DTX2 by voluntary ingestion was 1202 µg/kg confirming its lower toxicity profile (Abal et al., 2017). These findings may have more impact in Japan and Canada where DTX1 is more prevalent in the marine areas as compared to OA which is more prevalent in Europe (Rodríguez et al., 2015). Previously, DTX1 was described as more potent than OA (Suzuki and Okada, 2018). In fact, the relative inhibition of PP2A of the DTX-1 is higher than OA. Still, DSTs may have other molecular targets responsible of their toxicity (Espiña et al., 2010; Munday, 2013).

Risk assessments of DSTs require toxicity equivalency factors (TEFs) which provide a measure of the toxic potency of an analogue with respect to a reference compound. No human death by DSP has been reported, therefore median lethal dose (LD₅₀) is not accurate to determine TEF values for DSTs. Identification of indicators/processes that can be reliably used to quantify the overall toxicity, are the big goals in this field for the near future. To accurately reflect Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning, the ED₅₀ we determined for the incidence of diarrhea should be considered. With these doses we can set TEF values (OA 1; DTX1 1.1; DTX2 0.25) that ensure accurate risk assessment.

In conclusion, our study provides an evaluation of the acute toxicity profile of OA, DTX1 and DTX2 via voluntary intake in mice. Our goal was to incorporate an administration route that more accurately reflected the human exposure and increased the reliability of the effects observed in animal models. We reported dose-dependent clinical signs including diarrhea within the first 3 h post-administration. In particular, ED₅₀ values for watery diarrhea consistently indicate that DTX2 is significantly less toxic than OA and DTX1. Based on these doses we were able to determine TEF values. Overall, our work provides valuable insights for refining risk assessments and regulatory standards for marine toxins.

Compliance with standards

The manuscript does not contain clinical studies or patient data.

Code availability

GraphPad Prism were the software used to perform statistical analysis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Celia Costas: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Eva Cagide:** Visualization, Formal analysis. **Luis M. Botana:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Luis Rodríguez-Santos:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **M. Carmen Louzao:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mercedes R. Vieytes:** Supervision. **Manuel Lolo:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Carmen Vale:** Formal analysis. **Natalia Vilariño:** Investigation. **Cristina Carrera:** Investigation. **Mercedes Alvarez:** Investigation. **Almudena Graña:** Investigation.

Consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Ethics approval

All animal procedures were carried out in compliance with the European (EU directive 2010/63/EU), the Spanish legislation (Real Decreto 53/2013, Decreto 296/2008) and with the principles approved

by the Institutional Animal Care Committee of the University of Santiago de Compostela under the procedure Code: 01/17/LU-002 (approved on 22 September 2017).

Research involving animals

Ethical compliance with current legislation is stated below.

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Declaration of Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.118864.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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